

DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. Digital technologies have made a paradigm shift in the entire education system. It is not only a knowledge provider but also a co-creator of information, a mentor, and an assessor. Technological improvements in education have made life easier for students. Instead of using pen and paper, students nowadays use various software and tools to create presentations and projects. When compared to a stack of notebooks, an iPad is relatively light. When opposed to a weighty book, surfing an E-book is easier. The article is investigating what does digital learning look like in education? How can you use it in class, and what are the advantages and disadvantages?

Keywords: digital learning, education, tools, technology, software, social media.

Digital learning is any kind of learning that employs technology. It is part of the everyday life of your pupils, often in the form of social media, multimedia, online games, and mobile phones. But what does digital learning look like in education?

When we talk about digital learning, what we really mean is the process of taking part in a lesson on any subject while using technology, most frequently the internet. A blog, a video, a live lecture or seminar, or even just an audio file can all be used for digital learning. At least one piece of technology, such as a computer, laptop, or smartphone, will be used in digital learning. It is frequently used interchangeably with distance learning, which describes those who study outside of a school, college, or university. The Open University is a fantastic illustration of distant education, and if all of the lessons are completed online, this would also be referred to as digital learning.

What distinguishes e-learning from digital learning?

You might be familiar with the phrase "e-learning," which described online learning. The phrases are very similar since e-learning is now regarded as a crucial component of digital learning, which has broadened to cover other

subjects. Digital learning has adopted the term to refer to the use of devices and the internet for learning. Digital learning often gives students the opportunity to speed up or slow down their work and choose where learning takes place (such as distance learners). In some cases, we can also give students flexibility as to which parts of the course or continuing education program they want to take. Digital learning has some amazing benefits! Two of the most notable are the ability to communicate with others without having to attend one place or enroll in a costly full course. You can study the same content. No matter where you are, you can access learning materials from anywhere, often eliminating the need to travel. A lot of digital learning is typically done using computers, laptops, and phones, giving you more opportunities to back up your completed work. You can save the file locally on your computer or upload it to a cloud-based storage system such as Google Drive or The Cloud. This usually means you can access your files on multiple devices wherever you are.

Digital learning has other benefits. Instantly find and correct spelling, punctuation, and grammatical errors as you word-process your essay or report. It also eliminates uncertainty about what a word means, as the various scripts are more or less readable.

Disadvantages of digital learning

The biggest disadvantage of digital learning is the information divide. The digital divide is the percentage of people who have access to the internet or digital devices and the percentage of people who don't. Digital learning is not an option for those who do not have access to an internet connection, computer, or mobile phone. Digital learning requires the use of digital devices. For some families this is not always possible. Many families still have access only to shared digital devices such as desktop computers, some have no computers at all, and a monthly fee for Internet access is a luxury. In many cases, it also means access to word processing or spreadsheet software. These packages can cost a lot of money, but fortunately some companies are working hard to make these resources available in the browser for free. Digital learning also means that students enrolled in digital learning courses and educational programs must possess a certain level of digital competence in order to be successful in their studies. For someone who has never used a computer or the internet, this can have a big impact on how easily they can understand the material and contribute to the lesson. , microphone, and speakers), send emails, and upload your work.

Digital Learning Tools

- Word processing software to create documents

- PowerPoint presentations or other slides
 - Digital or online flashcards
 - Game design software
 - Interactive whiteboards
- Online quizzes and educational games

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